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Shaping Satisfied Online Shoppers: Exploring Attitude, Value, and Trust Impact in Online Shopping Services among STIE AMM Mataram’s Shopee Users

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ABSTRACT

This research analyzes the influence of Attitude, Values, and Trust on Consumer Satisfaction in online shopping services among Shopee users, particularly students of STIE AMM Mataram. Through this study, factors contributing to the formation of Consumer Satisfaction in the increasingly vital e-commerce context can be identified. Data was collected from the population of STIE AMM Mataram students using Shopee. Multiple linear regression analysis reveals that Attitude, Values, and Trust collectively have a significant impact on Consumer Satisfaction. These findings demonstrate that the combination of individual perspectives on services, the values they uphold, and the level of trust in the e-commerce platform collectively influence the extent to which consumers feel content with their online shopping experience. Furthermore, the results indicate that Values and Trust have significant partial effects, while Attitude does not significantly impact Consumer Satisfaction. This conclusion offers essential insights for e-commerce practitioners and policymakers to optimize online shopping service strategies, including enhancing features in line with consumer values and strengthening customer trust. This research stimulates further studies to delve deeper into the interaction of these factors and their application in other e-commerce platforms as well as different demographic groups.

1. Introduction

Technological advancements have brought about the development of the internet as a platform for electronic commerce, or e-commerce. The use of the internet in e-commerce provides numerous advantages, such as technological advancements, faster communication and transactions, as well as better control over customer service. Many people worldwide are interested in engaging in online shopping, with various products being sold online at competitive prices.

Several factors drive consumers to choose online shopping. Consumers shop online for the convenience and enjoyment it offers. This is because consumers can shop online anytime and anywhere. The benefits consumers perceive from online shopping include time and cost savings, as buyers don't need to go to physical stores.

In recent times, many consumers have shifted to online purchases due to easy access, the convenience of comparing products, and flexible timing. This trend has led to an increasing demand for online shopping services in society. However, despite the advantages of online shopping services, many consumers still feel dissatisfied with the services provided by online shopping service providers. The causes can stem

from attitude (Selviana & Setyowati, 2019; Wardhana & Budianita, 2020; Lesnussa & Warbal, 2023), values (Dirgantara, 2013; Arif, 2018; Krisnanto & Yulianthini, 2021), and trust (Setyani, 2014; Salam, 2019; Anita, 2019).

Kotler & Keller (2018) state that consumer satisfaction is a feeling of pleasure or disappointment that arises when the performance (outcome) of a product is compared to the performance (or outcome) expected. Consumers will experience dissatisfaction and disappointment if the service does not meet expectations or falls below them. However, a consumer will feel satisfied if the service meets their expectations and delighted if it exceeds them.

Meanwhile, attitude is one of the factors that influence consumer satisfaction towards service providers. According to marketing experts, attitude can refer to an individual's views or evaluations of an object, idea, or situation that influence consumer behavior and reflect feelings, beliefs, and intentions towards a specific entity, such as a brand, product, or service (Hawkins & Mothersbaugh, 2013). In the context of online shopping services, service providers with positive and responsive attitudes towards consumers will be preferred by consumers and achieve higher satisfaction levels.

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Online shopping service providers who exhibit a positive attitude towards consumers will strive to provide better services. They will respond quickly to consumer requests and complaints and offer satisfying solutions (Wardhana & Budianita, 2020). Online shopping service providers with increasingly positive attitudes and responsiveness towards consumers will be preferred and attain higher consumer satisfaction (Lesnussa & Warbal, 2023). Therefore, it is important to enhance attitudes in service to make consumers feel valued and satisfied with the provided online shopping services.

Next is the value offered by service providers, which significantly influences consumer satisfaction. In the context of online shopping services, service providers that align with consumers' values are favored and achieve higher satisfaction levels. Online shopping service providers that offer quality products, reasonable prices, and good product availability will be preferred by consumers, leading to satisfaction (Dirgantara, 2013). Additionally, service providers who prioritize security and consumer privacy in online transactions will be respected and achieve higher satisfaction (Arif, 2018).

Consumer trust also plays a crucial role in influencing consumer satisfaction. Consumer trust is the positive belief held by consumers regarding the reliability, quality, and integrity of a brand, company, or product (Solomon et al, 2019). Consumer trust arises when consumers are confident that a company or brand will fulfill its promises and provide expected satisfaction. Before deciding to purchase a product, factors such as transaction security, service quality, consumer privacy, and testimonials from other consumers need to be considered. This way, we can choose trustworthy service providers and attain higher satisfaction from the services provided (Setyani, 2014).

In recent years, online shopping has experienced tremendous growth in Indonesia, thanks to rapid technological advancements and widespread internet penetration. In the online shopping ecosystem, Shopee has managed to capture consumer attention and become a widely favored platform. Consumers tend to prefer Shopee over other marketplaces like Tokopedia, Bukalapak, Lazada, and Blibli for online shopping. According to SimilarWeb data, Shopee is the e-commerce platform with the highest average site visits, with around 157.9 million visits per month.

One of the main reasons Shopee attracts many consumers is its intuitive and user-friendly interface. The Shopee app offers a seamless shopping experience with straightforward navigation and easily understandable features. Consumers can easily search for products, compare prices, and conduct transactions quickly. Additionally, Shopee offers various appealing promotions and offers that tempt consumers to shop on this platform.

Shopee is renowned for its competitive pricing and frequently provides enticing discounts, such as the "Shopee 9.9 Super Shopping Day" or "Shopee 12.12 Birthday Sale". Shopee has built a positive reputation for consumer protection through the "Shopee Guarantee" feature. The platform also incorporates social features that allow users to interact and share shopping experiences, including live streaming events involving celebrities or influencers to promote products. Shopee has successfully established a reliable logistics system and offers fast delivery through the "Shopee Express" feature.

Shopee's intuitive and user-friendly user interface provides an enjoyable online shopping experience for consumers. Each consumer can easily and quickly browse products, view user reviews, and compare prices. Features like chatting with sellers, a secure payment system, and real-time shipment tracking also enhance consumer trust in online shopping on Shopee.

In addition to catering to the general public's consumer needs, Shopee also offers various products that target the student segment, ranging from books, stationery, clothing, to gadgets. Students can easily find the products they need, thanks to efficient search features and clear categories. This product diversity offers flexibility for students to fulfill their needs within a

single platform.

Students are an active group in online shopping and often use e-commerce platforms. They often have unique shopping preferences and needs. Factors such as limited budgets, a desire for affordable products, and preferences for specific items can influence their online shopping behavior. By studying Shopee users who are students, this research can gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing consumer satisfaction in online shopping, especially for the student group.

Students might have different views and attitudes toward online shopping platforms compared to other consumer groups. For instance, they might trust specific platforms more or have a more positive attitude towards using technology in shopping activities. By focusing the research on students from STIE AMM Mataram, this study can uncover differences in their trust, values, and attitudes toward Shopee and understand their impact on consumer satisfaction.

In the competitive world of e-commerce, Shopee's ability to provide reliable logistics and fast delivery is a significant advantage. This provides an additional reason for consumers to choose Shopee as a trusted and dependable online shopping platform. However, the success of online shopping service providers like Shopee doesn't exempt them from challenges. There are still several issues in the field, such as delayed shipments, discrepancies between ordered and received items, and payment problems.

Although there have been previous studies examining factors influencing consumer satisfaction in the context of online shopping, there is still a lack of understanding about how individual attitudes, values, and trust specifically contribute to consumer satisfaction in using online shopping platforms. Previous research has tended to focus more on the technical aspects and features of e-commerce platforms, while the psychological aspects and individual perceptions of online shopping platforms have not been fully explored. In the context of STIE AMM Mataram students, who might have different preferences and needs in online shopping, factors like attitudes, values, and trust can uniquely influence consumer satisfaction.

By specifically examining Shopee users among STIE AMM Mataram students, this research aims to deepen the understanding of how consumer attitudes, their held values, and the level of trust in Shopee play a role in shaping their satisfaction as consumers. By scrutinizing the roles of these factors, this research can provide a significant contribution to enhancing the understanding of how online shopping service providers can improve consumer satisfaction and meet the specific needs of Shopee users, particularly among STIE AMM Mataram students. Additionally, it will offer guidance for future efforts in the development and enhancement of e-commerce services.

In this study, attitudes, values, and trust are chosen as the variables influencing consumer satisfaction in online shopping. Meanwhile, consumer satisfaction serves as the dependent variable. The objective of this research is to analyze the influence of attitudes, values, and trust on consumer satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services, particularly among STIE AMM Mataram students who use Shopee.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Consumer Satisfaction

Consumer satisfaction, as defined by Kotler & Keller (2018), is "the feeling of pleasure or disappointment that an individual experiences after comparing the performance (outcome) of a product they perceived against the performance (outcome) they expected." Therefore, measuring the level of consumer satisfaction is crucial for the sustainability of a company. Addressing service quality and

customer satisfaction issues is relatively more challenging compared to measuring physical product or goods satisfaction.

2.2. Attitudes

Attitudes cannot be directly observed but must be inferred from what people say or what they do. There is a common consensus that attitudes are "learned." This means that attitudes related to purchasing behavior are formed as a result of direct product experiences, orally acquired information from others, or exposure to advertising through mass media, the internet, and various forms of direct marketing (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2007).

2.3. Values

According to Zeithaml et al (2002) and Sweeney & Soutar (2001), customer value is the overall assessment by customers of the utility of a product based on perceptions of what is received and what is given. Meanwhile, according to Rangkuti (2006), customer value is a comprehensive assessment of the benefits of a product, based on customers' perceptions of what is gained in relation to the costs incurred.

2.4. Trust

Trust is an essential aspect for a commitment or promise, and commitment can only be realized when it holds significance over time. Morgan and Hunt, as mentioned in Dharmmestha & Irawan (2008), argue that when one party has confidence that the other party engaged in an exchange is reliable and has integrity, trust can be said to exist. Moorman et al, as cited by Dharmmestha & Irawan (2008), define trust as an individual's willingness to rely on the other party involved in the exchange because of their confidence in that party. Trust is a general expectation that individuals hold, that the words spoken by the other party can be relied upon. Trust is believing in and having confidence in a partner in a relationship..

3. Research Method

The research method employed in this study is associative research. According to Sugiyono (2015), associative research aims to understand the relationship between two or more variables. This research is intended to determine the influence of attitudes, values, and trust on consumer satisfaction in the provision of Shopee's online shopping services. Through this research, a theory will be developed that can serve to explain, predict, and control a phenomenon.

Population refers to the entire set of objects or phenomena being studied (Sugiyono, 2015). The generalized population consists of objects or subjects that possess specific quantities and characteristics defined by the researcher for study and from which conclusions can be drawn (Kriyantono, 2014). The provision of online shopping services under study is focused on Shopee users, simplifying the process of selecting research samples. The population of this research comprises all STIE AMM Mataram students who are consumers of Shopee's online shopping services. The population in this research falls under an unknown population.

A sample is a subset of the population with its own characteristics (Sugiyono, 2015). A sample consists of objects from the population that are selected using sampling techniques, methods used to reduce the research objects to a representative subset. The sample unit in this study consists of a subset of students who are consumers of Shopee's online shopping services.

The sampling technique employed is accidental sampling, a technique based on the premise that individuals who happen to come across or incidentally encounter the researcher can be considered as samples if they are suitable as data sources (Sugiyono, 2015). The population under study

includes every STIE AMM Mataram student who is a consumer of Shopee's online shopping services, with 60 respondents.

The data collection tool utilized in this study is an online questionnaire. The questionnaire is distributed to respondents through Google Form. The questionnaire in this study consists of statements regarding the influence of attitudes, values, and trust on consumer satisfaction.

Multiple linear regression analysis is used when the researcher intends to predict how the state (increase or decrease) of the dependent variable (criterion) changes when two or more independent variables act as predictor factors (in influencing the value changes). Thus, multiple regression analysis is performed when there are at least two independent variables (Sugiyono, 2015). The analysis employed in this study is the technique of multiple linear regression analysis, expressed as the regression equation:

$$Y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + b_3X_3 + e$$

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Data Analysis

In this discussion, data analysis will be conducted to explain the results of the survey that has been conducted regarding the influence of attitudes, values, and trust on consumer satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services. This will lead to answers to the hypotheses that were previously formulated. First, validity and reliability testing will be performed on the questionnaire to ensure the accuracy and trustworthiness of the instrument, making it a dependable tool for data collection. Validity testing utilizes the Corrected Item-Total Correlation, while reliability testing employs the reliability coefficient (Cronbach's Alpha), both conducted using the SPSS software.

The results of the questionnaire's validity testing, as seen in the appendix, will be presented in the following table:

TABLE I. RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE VALIDITY TEST RESULTS

Item	r Value	r Critical	Criteria
X1.1	0.827	0.300	Valid
X1.2	0.888	0.300	Valid
X1.3	0.683	0.300	Valid
X2.1	0.968	0.300	Valid
X2.2	0.866	0.300	Valid
X2.3	0.968	0.300	Valid
X3.1	0.630	0.300	Valid
X3.2	0.760	0.300	Valid
X3.3	0.775	0.300	Valid
Y1.1	0.711	0.300	Valid
Y1.2	0.604	0.300	Valid
Y1.3	0.553	0.300	Valid
Y1.4	0.698	0.300	Valid

Source: data analysis results.

From the results of the validity testing for the research questionnaire, as shown in Table I, it can be inferred that the validity testing outcomes for the research questionnaire regarding the influence of Attitudes, Values, and Trust on Consumer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services for Shopee users among STIE AMM Mataram students, are overall valid. This is indicated by the calculated r value being greater than the critical r value or r calculated > 0.300. Referring to the testing process to measure the extent to which the questionnaire or data collection instrument used in this study genuinely measures what is intended and whether it can be

relied upon as a valid tool for gathering data related to the influence of Attitudes, Values, and Trust on Consumer Satisfaction in the provision of Shopee's online shopping services.

Overall, the research questionnaire used to collect data regarding the influence of Attitudes, Values, and Trust on Consumer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services for Shopee users among STIE AMM Mataram students has proven to be valid. In other words, the questionnaire has demonstrated reliability and accuracy in measuring the variables under investigation. This outcome is a positive one as it confirms that the data collection instrument used is valid and reliable for this research, thereby enhancing confidence in the validity of the research findings.

Next, the results of the questionnaire's reliability testing for each variable in this study, as seen in the appendix, will be presented in the following table:

TABLE II. RESEARCH QUESTIONNAIRE RELIABILITY TEST RESULTS

Variable	Alpha Cronbach	Alpha Critical	Criteria
Attitudes (X ₁)	0.827	0.600	Reliable
Values (X ₂)	0.873	0.600	Reliable
Trust (X ₃)	0.786	0.600	Reliable
Consumer Satisfaction (Y)	0.746	0.600	Reliable

Source: data analysis results.

Based on the table above, the values for the overall alpha of the research questionnaire regarding the influence of Attitudes, Values, and Trust on Consumer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services for Shopee users among STIE AMM Mataram students are reliable, as they have a Cronbach's Alpha above 0.700, making them suitable for the next stage. Referring to the calculated Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient for all items or questions in the research questionnaire, they are consistently and reliably measuring the variables under investigation. In other words, this questionnaire has proven to be consistent and reliable in measuring the variables under study, which are the influence of Attitudes, Values, and Trust on Consumer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services for Shopee users among STIE AMM Mataram students, enhancing the validity of the research results and allowing for more convincing interpretations.

The variables in this study consist of respondent answers to the variables of Attitudes, Values, Trust, and Consumer Satisfaction in the provision of Shopee's online shopping services.

TABLE III. FREQUENCY DISTRIBUTION SCORES

Variable	Score	Criteria
Attitudes (X ₁)	3.66	Good
Values (X ₂)	3.66	Good
Trust (X ₃)	3.53	Good
Consumer Satisfaction (Y)	3.57	Good

Source: data analysis results.

The respondents' average scores for Attitudes, as displayed in Table III, is 3.66, falling into the "good" category. This indicates that the majority of respondents hold a positive or close-to-positive attitude towards the aspects measured by those indicators. A score of 3.66 within the 1 to 5 scale range suggests that respondents tend to agree or have supportive views regarding the Attitudes variable being measured. Although this outcome signifies a positive attitude, it's important to remember that interpreting scores needs to be considered within the context of the research, data collection methods, and broader analysis objectives.

The responses from students who are Shopee users regarding the Values variable reflect their perceptions of how much the platform meets

their expectations and needs. With an average score of 3.66 on a 1 to 5 rating scale, labeled as "good", this result indicates that the majority of Shopee-using students hold a positive or close-to-positive perception of the values provided by the platform. This score demonstrates that most respondents feel that Shopee provides the expected benefits and fulfills their desires in terms of product quality, competitive pricing, diverse options, and satisfactory customer service.

The users' responses towards the Trust variable depict the extent of their trust in the platform. With an average score of 3.53 on a 1 to 5 rating scale, categorized as "good", this result indicates that the majority of respondents tend to have a positive or close-to-positive trust in Shopee as an online shopping platform. This score reflects that most respondents feel comfortable and have confidence in the reliability, security, and quality of services provided by Shopee.

Respondents' feedback regarding the Satisfaction variable in online shopping through the Shopee application portrays their evaluation of the shopping experience they've had. With an average score of 3.57 classified as "good", this result shows that the majority of respondents feel satisfied with their shopping experience through the Shopee application. This score indicates that respondents perceive a high level of comfort and satisfaction in various aspects, such as easy app navigation, products meeting expectations, smooth transaction experiences, and satisfactory customer service. The interpretation of these results should be adjusted for respondent characteristics and the online shopping environment, and can serve as a reference for Shopee to continuously enhance features and services to maintain and improve user satisfaction in shopping through their app platform.

Moving forward to analyze the data, multiple linear regression analysis is employed, with first creating equations to determine if the constructed model meets the criteria or not, based on the following Table IV:

TABLE IV. THE INFLUENCE OF ATTITUDES, VALUES, AND TRUST ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION IN ONLINE SHOPPING SERVICE PROVISION AMONG SHOPEE USERS AMONG STIE AMM MATARAM STUDENTS

Model	Coefficients			t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	0.717	0.324		2.216	0.031
X ₁	0.056	0.086	0.058	0.653	0.517
X ₂	0.281	0.073	0.357	3.875	0.000
X ₃	0.575	0.069	0.661	8.305	0.000

Source: data analysis results.

From Table IV, the regression coefficients of the research variables can be explained as follows:

$$Y = 0.717 + 0.056 X_1 + 0.281 X_2 + 0.575 X_3$$

The constant value of 0.717 indicates that the average Customer Satisfaction score is 0.717 when the company management does not implement Attitudes, Values, and Trust. This suggests that Customer Satisfaction in online shopping service provision among Shopee users among STIE AMM Mataram students would show a very low level without the implementation of Attitudes, Values, and Trust, indicating that these factors are crucial for forming Customer Satisfaction.

The influence of the Attitudes variable (X₁) on the formation of Customer Satisfaction (Y) in online shopping service provision among Shopee users among STIE AMM Mataram students, based on calculations using the SPSS program, results in a regression coefficient of 0.056. The positive sign indicates a positive or direct relationship. This means that for every 1-unit increase in the Attitudes variable, Customer Satisfaction increases by 0.056 units, assuming that Values

and Trust are constant. From the conducted analysis, it can be stated that higher Attitudes lead to higher Customer Satisfaction. Conversely, if Attitudes decrease, Customer Satisfaction will also decrease.

The influence of the Values variable (X_2) on the formation of Customer Satisfaction (Y) in online shopping service provision among Shopee users among STIE AMM Mataram students, based on calculations using the SPSS program, results in a regression coefficient of 0.281. The positive sign indicates a positive or direct relationship. This means that for every 1-unit increase in the Values variable, Customer Satisfaction increases by 0.281 units, assuming that Attitudes and Trust are constant. From the conducted analysis, it can be stated that higher Values lead to higher Customer Satisfaction. Conversely, if Values decrease, Customer Satisfaction will also decrease.

The influence of the Trust variable (X_3) on the formation of Customer Satisfaction (Y) in online shopping service provision among Shopee users among STIE AMM Mataram students, based on calculations using the SPSS program, results in a regression coefficient of 0.575. The positive sign indicates a positive or direct relationship. This means that for every 1-unit increase in the Trust variable, Customer Satisfaction increases by 0.575 units, assuming that Attitudes and Values are constant. From the conducted analysis, it can be stated that higher Trust leads to higher Customer Satisfaction. Conversely, if Trust decreases, Customer Satisfaction will also decrease in the online shopping service provision among Shopee users among STIE AMM Mataram students.

The coefficient of determination (R^2) essentially measures the extent to which the model explains the variation in the independent variables. The calculation using the SPSS program yields the following result:

TABLE V. RESULTS OF THE COEFFICIENT OF DETERMINATION TEST (R^2)

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.826	0.683	0.666	0.19349

Source: data analysis results.

Based on the table above, the multiple linear regression coefficient of determination (Adjusted R^2) obtained is 0.666 or 66.60 percent. This means that the variables Attitude, Value, and Trust contribute or provide a contribution in shaping Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students, by 66.60 percent. The remaining 33.40 percent is caused by other variables outside the scope of the study.

The multiple linear regression coefficient of determination is a statistical measure that indicates the extent to which the variation in the Customer Satisfaction variable can be explained by the Attitude, Value, and Trust variables that are the focus of the study. The R^2 value ranges from 0 to 1, and the higher the value, the better the model's ability to explain the variation in the dependent variable (Customer Satisfaction) based on the independent variables (Attitude, Value, and Trust). About 66.60 percent of the variation in Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students, can be explained by the combined influence of the Attitude, Value, and Trust variables. This indicates that these three variables have a significant contribution in shaping Customer Satisfaction.

This study found that the Attitude, Value, and Trust variables together have a significant influence on Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students. With a contribution rate of 66.60 percent, these variables play an important role in influencing consumer preferences and actions regarding Customer Satisfaction. This information can assist Shopee's management in better understanding the factors influencing Customer Satisfaction and enhancing their marketing strategies to achieve further success.

To test whether the independent variables Attitude, Value, and Trust have a role in influencing Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students, the F-test can be used. The results of the F-test calculation using SPSS will be presented below:

TABLE VI. RESULTS OF THE F TEST

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	4.512	3	1.504	40.169	0.000
	Residual	2.097	56	0.037		
	Total	6.608	59			

Source: data analysis results.

From the ANOVA test results table, it can be observed that the calculated F value is 40.169 with a significance level of 0.000. When compared with the critical F value determined from the table at a 5 percent significance level, with $df_1 = 3$ and $df_2 = 60$, the critical F value is 2.430. Since the calculated F value (40.169) is greater than the critical F value (2.430), we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_a). This implies that the variables Attitude, Value, and Trust simultaneously have a significant influence on the formation of Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students.

The t-test is used to examine the significance of the individual influence of each variable, namely Attitude, Value, and Trust, on the formation of Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students. The following are the results of the t-test calculations and the significance levels of each independent variable on the dependent variable, as shown in the table below:

TABLE VII. RESULTS OF THE T TEST

Variable	t	Sig.	Description
Attitudes (X_1)	0.653	0.517	Insignificant
Values (X_2)	3.875	0.000	Significant
Trust (X_3)	8.305	0.000	Significant

Source: data analysis results.

The significance level of the Attitude variable (X_1) on the formation of Customer Satisfaction (Y) in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students, resulted in a calculated t-value of 0.653 with a significance value of 0.517. When comparing the calculated t-value of 0.653 with the tabulated t-value of 2.009, it can be seen that the calculated t-value is smaller than the tabulated t-value, which means that the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is rejected and the null hypothesis (H_0) is accepted. This can also be observed from the comparison of the significance value achieved, which is 0.517, indicating a significance level higher than 5 percent. Thus, the Attitude variable has an insignificant influence on the formation of Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students. A positive value indicates a positive or direct relationship. This means that higher Attitude values would correspond to higher Customer Satisfaction, and conversely, lower Attitude values would decrease Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students.

The significance level of the Value variable (X_2) on the formation of Customer Satisfaction (Y) in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students, resulted

in a calculated t-value of 3.875 with a significance value of 0.000. When comparing the calculated t-value of 3.875 with the tabulated t-value of 2.009, it can be seen that the calculated t-value is larger than the tabulated t-value, which means that the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted and the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. This can also be observed from the comparison of the significance value achieved, which is 0.000, indicating a significance level lower than 5 percent. Thus, the Value variable has a significant influence on the formation of Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students. A positive value indicates a positive or direct relationship. This means that higher Value values would correspond to higher Customer Satisfaction, and conversely, lower Value values would decrease Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, STIE AMM Mataram students.

The significance level of the Trust variable (X_3) related to the formation of Customer Satisfaction (Y) in the context of providing online shopping services among Shopee users, who are students of STIE AMM Mataram, was measured using the t-test statistic, resulting in a calculated t-value of 8.305 and a significance value of 0.000. Comparing the calculated t-value of 8.305 with the critical t-value of 2.009, it can be concluded that the calculated t-value is significantly larger than the tabulated t-value. This implies that the alternative hypothesis (H_a) is accepted, while the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected. This conclusion is further supported by the fact that the achieved significance value is 0.000, indicating that the level of error is lower than the 5 percent threshold.

Therefore, it can be suggested that the Trust variable significantly impacts the formation of Customer Satisfaction in the realm of providing online shopping services among Shopee users, who are students of STIE AMM Mataram. The positive orientation of this value indicates a positive relationship, meaning that higher levels of Trust correspond to increased Customer Satisfaction. Conversely, if Trust is low, its negative impact could reduce the level of Customer Satisfaction within the framework of providing online shopping services among Shopee users, especially among STIE AMM Mataram students.

From the multiple linear regression model, it can be concluded that the dominant variable influencing the formation of Customer Satisfaction in the provision of online shopping services among Shopee users, who are students of STIE AMM Mataram, is the Trust variable (X_3). This conclusion is based on the highest calculated t-value (8.305) when compared to the Attitude (X_1) and Value (X_2) variables. Thus, the hypothesis stating that Trust is the dominant variable influencing Customer Satisfaction formation is supported by this research.

4.2. Research Findings and Discussions

This study aims to analyze and interpret the influence of three crucial factors, namely Attitude, Value, and Trust, on the process of forming Customer Satisfaction in the context of providing online shopping services among Shopee platform users, particularly among STIE AMM Mataram students. The rapid growth of e-commerce platforms has brought fundamental changes in consumer behavior, especially in this digital era. Therefore, a deeper understanding of how individuals' Attitude towards online shopping services, the Values they hold, and the level of Trust they possess in the platform can provide richer insights into the factors shaping Customer Satisfaction levels.

In the context of this study, Attitude is defined as individuals' perspectives and assessments of the online shopping services they use. Value refers to principles and beliefs guiding consumer choices. Meanwhile, Trust encompasses beliefs in the integrity, reliability, and security of the online shopping platform. This research involves the population of STIE AMM Mataram students who are active users of Shopee, as this group represents a significant portion of online shopping platform users and has unique consumer behavior tendencies.

Through an in-depth analysis of the impact of Attitude, Value, and Trust on the formation of Customer Satisfaction, this study is expected to offer valuable insights for e-commerce practitioners, policymakers, and academics to optimize the online shopping experience. The interpretative findings of this research can pave the way for more effective strategies in enhancing Customer Satisfaction in the context of online shopping services, providing a solid foundation for further developments in this field.

The results of this research indicate an interesting finding regarding the influence of Attitude on the formation of Customer Satisfaction in online shopping services among Shopee users who are students at STIE AMM Mataram. Surprisingly, the influence of Attitude on Customer Satisfaction does not exhibit a significant level of significance. Although there was an assumption previously that an individual's Attitude towards online shopping services would have a strong impact on the level of Customer Satisfaction, as seen in findings by Selviana and Setyowati (2019); Wardhana and Budianita (2020); Lesnusa and Warbal (2023), this study's finding contradicts that notion.

One reason that can explain the lack of significance of Attitude towards the formation of Customer Satisfaction could be the complexity of factors influencing consumer preferences and decisions. It is possible that the Attitudes held by students towards online shopping services may not yet be the dominant factor in shaping Customer Satisfaction levels. Other factors such as past experiences, service quality, technical platform features, as well as interactions with customers and sellers, could also have a more significant impact on the formation of Customer Satisfaction.

Furthermore, these findings could also indicate the presence of external factors influencing individual Attitudes in the context of online shopping. Attitudes can be influenced by cultural factors, social perspectives, or information available in the surrounding environment. There is a possibility that these influences may not be fully reflected in the questionnaire or data collected in this research.

Overall, the finding that the influence of Attitude is not significant in shaping Customer Satisfaction underscores the importance of considering the complexity of interacting factors in the e-commerce context. These results invite further research to identify other factors that may have a greater impact on Customer Satisfaction in online shopping services. Additionally, it is important to deepen the understanding of how these aspects can be intervened or managed to enhance the overall consumer experience.

The results of this study reveal significant facts regarding the influence of Value on the formation of Customer Satisfaction in the framework of providing online shopping services among Shopee users who are students at STIE AMM Mataram. These findings demonstrate that the factor of Value plays an important role in shaping consumers' perceptions and evaluations of their online shopping experiences, as seen in the research by Dirgantara (2013); Arif (2018); Krisnanto and Yulianthini (2021). This finding indicates that the beliefs and principles held by students in the context of online shopping significantly contribute to the level of Customer Satisfaction they experience. Values that underlie consumer choices, such as shopping ethics, transaction fairness, or alignment with personal values, form a framework that guides their evaluation of service quality and the satisfaction they obtain.

In the context of online shopping services on the Shopee platform, students who have Value alignment with the way the platform operates tend to be more satisfied with their shopping experiences. This indicates that more abstract and value-oriented factors can have a substantial impact on consumers' perceptions of e-commerce services. This connection highlights the importance of a deep understanding of the values that underlie consumer behavior in

the digital environment.

These results also emphasize the need for e-commerce service providers to understand the dominant values among their consumers and align their strategies with these values. This might involve more transparent approaches, targeted communication, or even the development of features that support consumer value aspirations and needs. Overall, these findings provide a richer perspective on the essential role played by Value factors in shaping Customer Satisfaction in the realm of online shopping amidst the rapid growth of e-commerce platforms. These findings have important implications for business strategies and product development aimed at enhancing customer satisfaction and experience in the online shopping environment.

This study reveals prominent findings regarding the dominant influence of Trust on the formation of Customer Satisfaction in the context of providing online shopping services among Shopee users who are students at STIE AMM Mataram. These results indicate that the Trust factor plays a very strong role in shaping consumers' perceptions of their online shopping experiences. This finding confirms previous research findings (Setyani, 2014; Salam, 2019; Anita, 2019).

These findings demonstrate that students who have a higher level of Trust in the Shopee platform tend to experience a higher level of Customer Satisfaction as well. Similarly, if Trust is low, it will decrease the degree of Customer Satisfaction in online shopping. The Trust given by consumers to transaction security, product quality, customer service, and overall platform integrity provides a crucial foundation in determining the extent to which consumers feel satisfied with their shopping experience.

Trust being the dominant factor in shaping Customer Satisfaction in the context of online shopping is well-founded. The e-commerce environment, often occurring without direct interaction between sellers and buyers, requires consumers to place their Trust in the platform as an intermediary. Factors such as personal data security, delivery reliability, and product quality are crucial in building this Trust.

Solid Trust creates a sense of security and comfort for consumers, reducing the risks associated with online purchases. It also establishes the groundwork for long-term relationships between consumers and the platform, resulting in better customer loyalty and retention. In an uncertain environment like e-commerce, Trust becomes an invaluable foundation in shaping consumers' perceptions of the value and quality of services.

Thus, the results of these findings emphasize the importance for e-commerce platforms to continue investing in building and maintaining high levels of Trust among their consumers. Efforts to strengthen platform security, transparency, and reliability will directly contribute to improving Customer Satisfaction and long-term success in this competitive market.

5. Conclusion

The following are the research conclusions: 1) Through in-depth analysis, it is revealed that Attitude, Value, and Trust simultaneously have a significant influence on the formation of Customer Satisfaction; 2) It is found that Value and Trust partially have a significant impact on the formation of Customer Satisfaction, while Attitude is not proven to have a significant influence; 3) Trust is the dominant variable that affects the formation of Customer Satisfaction in the context of online shopping.

Based on the presented research results, several suggestions and recommendations can be proposed for further development in the context of analyzing the influence of Attitude, Value, and Trust on the formation of Customer Satisfaction in online shopping services on the Shopee platform users. Although in this study Attitude is not proven to have a significant impact on Customer Satisfaction, efforts to understand more specific dimensions of Attitude, such as perceptions of product features, services, or platform interfaces, could be an interesting area of research. This can provide deeper insights into how these more specific attitude factors can influence Customer Satisfaction.

References

- Anita, Y. (2019). Pengaruh harga, kualitas pelayanan dan kepercayaan terhadap kepuasan konsumen dalam perspektif ekonomi islam (studi pada bisnis online shop: Shopee, Tokopedia, Bukalapak, dan Lazada di kota Pekanbaru). *Master Thesis*, Program Pascasarjana (PPS) Universitas Islam Negeri (UIN) Sultan Syarif Kasim, Riau. <https://repository.uin-suska.ac.id/22786/1/YENI%20ANITA.pdf>
- Arif, M. (2018). Pengaruh nilai dan kepuasan pelanggan terhadap loyalitas (pelanggan pada PT. Sinar Galesong Mandiri Makassar). *Script*, Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Universitas Muhammadiyah, Makassar. <https://123dok.com/document/zw17mk1q-skripsi-pengaruh-nilai-dan-kepuasan-pelanggan-terhadap-loyalitas-pelanggan-pada-pt-sinar-galesong-mandiri-makassar-muhammad-arif.html>
- Dharmestha, B. S., & Irawan. (2008). *Manajemen Pemasaran Modern*. Yogyakarta: Liberty.
- Dirgantara, W. (2013). Pengaruh kualitas pelayanan dan nilai pelanggan terhadap kepuasan pengunjung Museum Kartini Jepara. *Management Analysis Journal*, 2(1), 110-117. <https://journal.unnes.ac.id/sju/index.php/maj/article/view/1954/1757>
- Hawkins, D. I., & Mothersbaugh, D. L. (2013). *Consumer Behavior: Building Marketing Strategy*. New York: McGraw-Hill Irwin. <https://aclasites.files.wordpress.com/2017/02/consumer-behavior-building-marketing-strategy-11th-edition.pdf>
- Ghozali, I. (2016). *Analisis Multivariate dengan IBM SPSS 23*. Semarang: Badan Penerbit Universitas Diponegoro.
- Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2018). *Manajemen Pemasaran*. Jakarta: Indeks.
- Krisnanto, A., & Yulianthini, N. N. (2021). Pengaruh nilai pelanggan dan kepercayaan terhadap kepuasan pelanggan pengguna jasa Gojek di Kota Singaraja. *PROSPEK: Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis*, 3(1):74-80. <https://ejournal.undiksha.ac.id/index.php/Prospek/article/view/30906/pdf>
- Kriyantono, R. (2014). *Teknik Praktis Riset Komunikasi*. Jakarta: Prenada Media.
- Lesnussa, J. U., & Warbal, M. (2023). Pengaruh sikap dan kualitas pelayanan terhadap kepuasan pelanggan. *Jurnal Public Policy*, 4(1):31-46. <https://stia-saidperintah.ejournal.id/ppj/article/view/117/78>
- Rangkuti, F. (2006). *Teknik Mengukur dan Strategi Meningkatkan Kepuasan Pelanggan*. Jakarta: Gramedia.
- Salam, F. R. (2019). Pengaruh kepercayaan pelanggan dan pelayanan terhadap kepuasan pelanggan pdam di Kecamatan Secanggung Kabupaten Langkat. *Script*, Fakultas Ekonomi dan Bisnis Islam Universitas Islam Negeri Sumatera Utara, Medan. <http://repository.uinsu.ac.id/7831/1/SKRIPSI%20FAHRUR%20RAJI%20SALAM.pdf>
- Schiffman, L. G., & Kanuk, L. L. (2007). *Perilaku Konsumen*, Edisi 7. Jakarta: Indeks.
- Selviana, & Setyowati, R. B. (2019). Pengaruh sikap belanja online terhadap trust melalui mediator kepuasan pelanggan. *Jurnal IKRAITH-HUMANIORA*, 3(2):58-64. <https://journals.upi-vai.ac.id/index.php/ikraith-humaniora/article/view/439/321>
- Setyani, L. A. (2014). Analisis pengaruh kualitas pelayanan dan kepercayaan terhadap loyalitas pelanggan melalui kepuasan pelanggan (studi pada griya kecantikan Aura Kota Semarang). *Script*, Fakultas Ekonomika dan Bisnis Universitas Diponegoro, Semarang. http://eprints.undip.ac.id/43361/1/02_SETYANI.pdf

- Solomon, M. R., Hogg, M. K., Askegaard, S., & Bamossy, G. (2019). *Consumer Behaviour: A European Perspective*, 7th Edition. Harlow: Pearson Longman.
- Sugiyono. (2015). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- Sweeney, J. C., & Soutar, G. N. (2001). Consumer perceived value: The development of a multiple item scale. *Journal of Retailing*, 77(2):203-220. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359\(01\)00041-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-4359(01)00041-0)
- Wardhana, M. A., & Budianita, A. (2020). Sikap konsumen pada belanja online Tokopedia efek kualitas layanan elektronik, kepercayaan dan kepuasan konsumen elektronik. *Jurnal Bisnis Digital dan Sistem Informasi*, 1(1):12-20. <https://ejr.umku.ac.id/index.php/BIDISFO/article/viewFile/889/547>
- Zeithaml, V. A., Parasuraman, A., & Malhotra, A. (2002). Service quality delivery through websites: a critical review of extant knowledge. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 30(4):362-75. <https://doi.org/10.1177/009207002236911>